

F-Theory & String Theory on Singular Spaces: A
Comprehensive Examination Of Implications On
Quantum Field Theory

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1 Abstract

F-Theory is a contemporary domain raised for the purpose of unifying the superstring theories of Quantum Field Theory(QFT). This paper dives into providing a solid introduction of topological characteristics of dimensional entities proposed by F-theory, alongside the implications that it has on a Unifying Field Theory. Alongside this, a thorough contextualization of String Theory is provided, alongside the consideration of M-Theory and U-theory as adjacent developments to the framework with F-theory itself, with an explanation of the multi-dimensional characteristics of strings and their reverberations towards reconciling Newtonian physics with Quantum Mechanics. We will consider the underlying meaning behind the described propositions and the effect that it could possibly have with future research in general particle physics; the defining question of this exploration seeks to explain the applicability of F-theory on String networks: To what extent does the multidimensional F-theory correlate with the observations made for three-dimensional particles? By conclusion, you will be thoroughly knowledgeable on the rudimentary structure of String Theory and the propositions that it makes at dimensional-levels that describe elementary particle-wave behavior. Alongside this, the study of F-theory and the potential of the study as an underlying mechanism to QFT will become apparent.

2 Introduction to String Theory

String theory was initially devised in 1968, being derived from Gabriele Veneziano's configuration of the strong nuclear force at linear trajectories. The consideration of hadrons – subatomic particles related to the strong force that consist of two quarks – as strings allowed for the rise of quantum properties unexplainable by any prior model in nature; by 1973, it was mathematically proven that the apparent nature of gravity could also be explained through the innate property of such quantized strings, which allowed for scientists to reconcile Newtonian Mechanics and Special Relativity. The reason that physicists appropriated such a task was for the furtherance of a concise formulation to explain the entirety of physics in a coherent theory. By this point in the 20th century, physicists had a more describable understanding of String theory properties and the dimensional analytics that seemed to be a dire problem for the field. String theory became established as a theoretical framework for quantum mechanics and, more precisely, quantum field theory in that it established the fundamental particles of quantum mechanics as string interactions rather than solid entities themselves. In the conceptual understanding of particle physics at the time, we were aware of elementary particles and the primary forces that dictated Strings, which were one-dimensional point objects that had a rigid structure and a vibrational character, and interacted with one another through fluctuations whilst having apparent Newtonian properties[1]. Once the model had become

apparent throughout physicists internationally, the bridge between prior theories regarding Quantum field theory and the theoretical frameworks of the future that were yet to be proven began to appear. For example, following Veneziano's publication, global frameworks began to consider the S-matrix, a complex and highly unviable theory that was devised by Werner Heisenburg to describe the alternation of subatomic particles through a realignment in their describable qualities. Given the perturbation of considering electrons as a point-based object, there was the theory that these particles were not independent objects, but rather a network of interconnected vibrations. The S-matrix model eventually became discontinued as the result of inaccuracies observed in the complex mathematics of condensed bodies. The S-matrix also attempted to deal with the formation of particles in free space, while it has been proven that String theory suggests no empty volume as a result of the vibrational strings that exist in all spaces[2]. After 1958, the framework that would later become String Theory took another drastic turn in the hands of Tullio Regge. Devising the Regge Theory of Quantum Mechanics, he formulated a concept known as the Regge trajectory, which describes angular momentum of strings in space when compared to their theoretical mass squared. The theory itself was revolutionary in that it not only found the rudimentary properties of such string aside from their mere mass or vibration in the form of angular momentum, but that it also could utilize any integer value n and any complex number η for the calculating of energy scattering in such strings as well. Reggae used the framework established by Colomb and his equation of electric potential[10]:

$$V(r) = -e^2 / (4\pi\epsilon_0 r)$$

In the above equation, the -e represents the electric charge and ϵ_0 represents the permittivity of the vacuum. This is simply describing the Coulomb potential as the binding of an electron in space. From here, Reggae assumed an Energy E, of which a negative E describes a release of energy with a negative charge and a positive E describes the absorption of energy with positive charge. With such assumptions, Reggae wrote the preliminary equation off which Veneziano was able to establish his framework[4]:

$$E \rightarrow E_N = -\frac{2m'\pi^2 e^4}{h^2 N^2 (4\pi\epsilon_0)^2} = -\frac{13.6 \text{ eV}}{N^2}, \quad m' = \frac{mM}{M+m},$$

In the above equation, Reggae was simply attempting to calculate the total energy E of the proton and the electron binding. Using the mass m of the electron, the charge e of an electron, the principal quantum number N, and the permittivity ϵ_0 (the quantitative distortion in a charge when an electric field is induced). With Veneziano becoming exposed to the domain, he was able to construct more on the implicit behavior that was noted in both the S-matrix proposition and the Regge Theory. Veneziano focused on the strong nuclear force as a unifying force that would help depict the scattering amplitude amongst closely charged masses, with protons and electrons within the atomic structure being the

key to such a description. He also noted inconsistencies within the theories and continuities that had to be continued through his theory: mass of the incoming particle should be equal to the mass of the outgoing particle, scattering should be perpendicular to poles, output of pole absorbance should be positive, and poles created with particle collisions. Through the conditionals and his prior work on Beta functions, Veneziano provided a solution in 1968 that involved a Beta function with the pole value and time as parameters[4]:

$$B(s, t) = \frac{\Gamma(-(s - \alpha(s)))\Gamma(-(t - \alpha(t)))}{\Gamma(-(s + t - \alpha(s + t)))}$$

2.1 F-Theory

As we were able to learn in the initial conception of String theory, it became apparent that the strings need a specialized medium to propagate with such medium having dimensions that are invisible to our eyes and instruments; in such theory, our viewing dimension is one that is perfectly perpendicular, so as to not reveal the given dimension in any way. F-Theory is a proposition that brings in the added complexity of 12 dimensions, opposed to the 10 in the original theory, which creates different points of string interaction that more closely resemble the particle behavior we know of[3]. In Newtonian physics, we observe the drastic changes that occur in kinematic calculations as we transition from one dimension to two dimensions and beyond, and this is a similar case in String Theory, where each added dimension adds compounding complexity and must be considered almost independently. Now, as a result of such a blunt increase in dimensions, we receive a greater number of theoretical manifolds, or areas of overlap within dimensional analysis, in the form of Calabi-Yau manifolds. The distinct geometry of a Calabi-Yau manifold brings with it a dainty balance of nature, where the number of folds can be calculated but not observed in any fashion. Like with F-theory and String Theory alike, such geometric topologies are part of the universal numbers game that humanity has engaged in[5]. The original F-Theory was proposed near the dawn of the 21st century by Cumrun Vafa and explained the ubiquitous flux compactifications that had been such a trivial entity in the original description of string theory. Flux compactifications are simply actions taken by the strings to induce background fluxes on the highly-dimensional particles to get them to form geometrically in our sphere of vision. While we are unable to observe the strings, we are able to observe the atomic particle and such a structure is allowed through flux compactifications itself. F-theory is a framework that allows physicists the possibility of discovering additional particle properties and the methods of manipulating such properties to bring about atomic fabrication, which would revolutionize our current understanding of quantum mechanics. Ultimately, the development of F-theory is not eminently modern, for it is simply a more elegant description of string theory with added complexity. The mathematics behind such a theory are far less underdeveloped than are the calculations made to prove the one-dimensional to ten-dimensional phenomenon. The most important

notion to understand in F-theory lies in the larger implications that it could possibly have on Quantum Field Theory.

3 Implications on Quantum Field Theory

3.1 F-Theory - Higgs Mechanics

Known to most as simply the God Particle, the Higgs Boson has left a remarkable print on the field of particle physics and quantum mechanics; though recently proved, the existence of such a Boson, even in theory, allowed for a more complete explanation of particle mass. It was an eminently hard particle to detect, with a perfectly-neutral spin, neutral charge, no known color, and doesn't actively interact with the strong nuclear force; in fact, it was with the Large Hadron Collider that we were able to confirm its existence. The Higgs Theory, the medium through which the Higgs Boson emerged, is an elegant one and allows for the consideration of particles as useless outside the force of any field. He posited that as particles accelerate through the Higgs Field, they interact with fluctuations and are dragged in a way that allows for mass, with the more massive objects interacting to a greater extent with such a field[6]. Now, where F-theory begins to reckon with the laws of physics comes about with its definition of mass, which slightly differs with the mass theory mentioned by Higgs in the 1960s. F-Theory provides that there is a mathematical framework to calculate particle mass with consideration of all 4 forces, particularly what the Higgs Theory was trying to solve through the assumption of zero mass where needed. This gives rise to a difficulty in creating a unified field theory, for not only do they stand in polarity on this particle notion, but they also differ in the number of dimensions through which fluctuations may occur. Whilst we know that F-Theory states that there are 12 dimensions of space time, the Higgs Field is a slightly more indecisive network that is said to exist primarily in the 4th dimension. These differences make it a complex challenge to unify the theories, but it needs to be done, for the topological properties of particles that are predicted by the F-Theory match that of the Higgs Theory and also allow for the greater study of Higgs Boson interaction with the elementary particles and forces. If the two are reconciled indefinitely, it would provide deep insights into the nature of mass creation and would unify the four fundamental forces, leading to a leap in the study for the so-called "Theory of Everything".

3.2 F-Theory - Supersymmetry

Supersymmetry is a fascinating concept; proposed by the standard model of physics, the theory of Supersymmetry suggests that fermions, particles under Fermi-Dirac statistics with a half-integer spin, and bosons, particles with a full-integer spin, demonstrate symmetry. With symmetry, the theory suggests that the fermions can be transformed

into bosons without changing the interactions of particles. Now, this might be a confusing paradigm, especially given that both these so-called particle partners have a differing set of quantum numbers and have a different unit of spin, but it has been mathematically proven as such[7]. For the preservation of conceptual understanding, we shall not delve into such mathematics in this paper, for they are eminently complex and exist in large sets, but we shall discuss their implications and the nature that they suggest. The reason for supersymmetry's popularity in particle physics is due to the strides that it made in bringing together the weak nuclear force and gravity in one theory, an issue that emerged during the calculation of the Higgs Boson interactions with particles on a quantum scale; based on the Planck spectrum of force or particle strength, the Higgs Boson lies on the bottom end, which creates a larger disparity between the weak force and gravity whilst aligning gravity with the other two. Now, based on supersymmetry, the existence of such superpartners in particles causes interactions that cancel out the issues mentioned by the Higgs Boson and allow for a stabilized mass prediction with little to no theoretical correction being needed. Now, compared to the reconciliation of F-theory with the Higgs theory, F-Theory can be more simply aligned with supersymmetry in that F-theory defines geometric properties, whilst supersymmetry quantum qualities. In fact, there is even a bridge between the two in the form of supergravity, which both theories adopt, which would not only bring about an additional ease in mathematical unification, but can also extend our current understanding of gravity in a way that has not been attempted yet. The most difficult polarity to bridge the two lies in the changes in superpartners with the rise of topological manifolds in spacetime, a rise in dimensions, and a more thorough description of particle geometry with strings; even this, however, is predicted to not disable supersymmetry from operating in symmetry with the F-Theory, so this is quite a promising endeavor that could finally solve the hierarchy problem and unify the forces[8].

4 Conclusion

In short, the field of F-Theory is one that does not show signals of slowing down and contains intrinsic properties that make it eminently unique as an extension to modern String theory. With the defining potential to bring about immense geometric and topological change to our current understanding of particles, F-Theory has the possibility to bring large strides within Quantum Field Theory and bring about a Grand Unified Field theory through several avenues of thought. Although many of the considered properties have not been observed in nature as of yet, F-Theory has the chance of moving towards the forefront of physics as we develop greater technology for the detection of strings.

5 References

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